

Zero Net Deforestation Goal and its effects on the expansion of agriculture in Mexico

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Context, Challenges, and Main Findings

- Mexico has 138 million forest hectares
- Deforestation rate of 0.38%
- Every year, around 47,770 hectares of forest are converted to cropland
- The Zero Deforestation Goal (ZDG) for 2030 was established (limit to cropland)
- **The implementation of the ZDG compromise the available supply but and modifies the production models of the country's three main crops.**

Scenarios

Using the OSeMOSYS the following scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
BAU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not measures to contain deforestation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest: 640 thousand square kilometers, • Annual deforestation rate (0.38%)
ZDG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest cover is not reduced • No cropland extension 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest no less than 640 thousand square kilometers • Crop demand increases as BAU (infeasible)
RDG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cropland extension is allowed until 2030 • Forest cover cannot be reduced after that year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest no less than 600 thousand square kilometers • A surplus of 40 thousand square kilometers for cropland until 2030, after that year forest cover cannot be reduced.

Results

- In the base scenario gradual reduction in the forest cover area in favor of rainfed corn crops.
- The scenario is infeasible, cropland must be expanded
- The ZDG scenario shows the containment of the deforestation. **It assumes an initial extra crop land area.**

- The irrigated land to sugar cane decreases, sorghum increases.
- The use of water for increases by 100%.
- The use of fuel for sorghum increases 48%.

Land use by crop

Water use by agro

Conclusions and Policy Insights

- The Zero Deforestation Goal cannot be achieved without compromising the supply of the analyzed crops.
- It is required to expand cropland, irrigated especially irrigated sorghum
- A greater amount of groundwater is required.
- Strategies improve existing irrigation systems
- Increase productivity
- Limit conversion of forest land

Future Work

Analyze the effects of the Zero Deforestation Policy on as many crops as possible.

Differentiate simulations by region